

Conditional Normalizing Flows for Probabilistic Harmonic Power Flow and Compliance Risk

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Abstract

Probabilistic harmonic power flow (PHPF) in distribution networks with high penetration of photovoltaic generation and electric vehicle charging requires extensive Monte Carlo simulation, particularly when compliance must be evaluated under specific operating conditions. Conventional Monte Carlo analysis provides marginal output distributions, but these cannot be directly conditioned on individual operating regimes.

We develop a conditional normalizing flow (CNF) surrogate that approximates the conditional distribution of per-bus harmonic voltages and total harmonic distortion indices given uncertain system states.

The surrogate achieves mean quantile errors of 0.005% and 0.011% at the 95th and 99th percentiles, respectively, a mean conditional exceedance error of 0.0009, and a probability integral transform deviation of 0.047, indicating accurate tail calibration. The results reveal strong regime dependence that is not visible in marginal statistics: at the most critical bus, the probability of exceeding the IEEE 519 limit of 8% ranges from approximately 0.10 under low-load conditions to approximately 0.91 under high-load conditions, whereas the marginal estimate is approximately 0.51. Once trained, the surrogate evaluates such conditional risk metrics in milliseconds through sampling, supporting rapid multi-scenario harmonic compliance analysis.

Keywords: Probabilistic harmonic power flow, Normalizing flows, Conditional generative models, Distribution networks, Harmonic compliance, Monte Carlo simulation

1. Introduction

The rapid integration of photovoltaic (PV) generation and electric vehicle (EV) charging into low- and medium-voltage distribution networks has reshaped the harmonic profile of modern grids. In contrast to conventional linear loads, power electronic converters inject harmonic currents across multiple frequency orders, with amplitudes and phase relationships that vary continuously with operating conditions. When several such sources operate simultaneously, as is increasingly typical in highly penetrated feeders, their aggregate contribution to voltage total harmonic distortion (THD) cannot be deduced from single-device behavior alone. Network topology, pre-existing background distortion, and statistical dependence among sources jointly determine a harmonic state that is strongly condition dependent.

Regulatory standards such as IEEE 519 [1] and EN 50160 [2] impose limits on harmonic voltage distortion at the point of common coupling (PCC). Demonstrating compliance therefore requires evaluation not only at nominal operating points, but across the range of plausible system conditions. Harmonic assessment is consequently probabilistic in nature: the relevant quantity is not a single deterministic THD value, but the probability that THD exceeds a prescribed threshold [3], paralleling chance-constrained formulations developed for fundamental-frequency operational constraints [4, 5].

Probabilistic harmonic power flow (PHPF) methods address this requirement by propagating uncertainty in PV output, load

demand, EV charging, and related operating variables through the harmonic network equations to characterize the resulting distribution of voltage distortion. Classical techniques include the Point Estimate Method (PEM) and linearization-based approaches, which approximate output moments using a limited number of deterministic evaluations or first-order expansions [6, 7]. Although computationally efficient, these approximations may lose accuracy under pronounced nonlinear conditions and do not directly recover the full output distribution needed for robust exceedance probability estimation.

Monte Carlo (MC) simulation remains the reference method for PHPF, since repeated sampling of uncertain inputs yields an empirical approximation of the joint output distribution with controllable statistical accuracy [8]. In distribution-scale networks, individual harmonic power flow evaluations are often expensive. MC campaigns, however, produce samples from the marginal distribution across all operating conditions. When compliance risk must be evaluated for a specific forecasted regime (for example, high solar penetration combined with elevated demand), additional conditional simulations are required. This limits flexibility in scenario-specific compliance analysis.

Recent studies have investigated machine learning surrogates to accelerate power system simulations, with most efforts concentrating on fundamental-frequency power flow and optimal power flow. These models typically target deterministic output prediction rather than learning the full output distribution. In contrast, harmonic power flow involves multi-frequency coupling

and nonlinear source behavior, and has received comparatively little attention in the surrogate modeling literature. Furthermore, point-estimate models are inherently limited for compliance assessment, where accurate characterization of tail probabilities is essential.

Generative models that learn complete conditional distributions offer a conceptually different approach. Among these, normalizing flows are well suited for scientific surrogate modeling: they are invertible, admit exact likelihood evaluation, and can be conditioned on arbitrary context variables [9]. In energy systems, conditional normalizing flows have been applied to probabilistic forecasting of wind generation, load, and weather-conditioned scenario generation [10, 11, 12]. Their use as surrogates for the *output distribution of multi-frequency harmonic power flow with explicit IEEE 519 compliance-risk inference* is, to the best of our knowledge, not reported in the literature surveyed.

In this work, we develop a conditional normalizing flow (CNF) surrogate for probabilistic harmonic power flow on the IEEE 33-bus distribution feeder. The model is trained on a large-scale Monte Carlo dataset generated under correlated stochastic operating conditions. The focus extends beyond computational acceleration to conditional risk inference: the CNF learns the joint distribution of harmonic voltages and THD indices conditioned on a given operating state, allowing direct evaluation of quantities such as

$$\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_V > \tau \mid \mathbf{x}),$$

where \mathbf{x} denotes the operating context and τ a regulatory threshold. The analysis shows that marginal exceedance probabilities can conceal pronounced regime-dependent effects, whereas conditional inference reveals substantial variation in compliance risk across operating conditions.

The main contributions of this work are summarized below:

- A conditional generative surrogate for probabilistic harmonic power flow that enables calibrated full-distribution inference rather than point prediction.
- A correlated uncertainty framework for distribution-level harmonic analysis and the generation of a large-scale Monte Carlo dataset.
- A quantitative comparison between marginal and conditional exceedance probabilities, highlighting their divergence and its implications for compliance assessment.
- A systematic evaluation of distributional calibration using quantile error metrics, conditional exceedance reliability, and probability integral transform (PIT) analysis.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 formulates the probabilistic harmonic power flow problem. Section 4 details the conditional normalizing flow methodology. Sections 5 and 6 describe the experimental setup and present the results. Section 7 discusses limitations and future research directions. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2. Related Work

2.1. Probabilistic Harmonic Power Flow

Probabilistic harmonic power flow (PHPF) extends deterministic harmonic analysis by explicitly accounting for uncertainty in load demand, distributed generation, and converter-based injections. Early work relied primarily on analytical uncertainty propagation. Point estimate methods approximate output moments by evaluating the harmonic power flow at a limited set of carefully chosen input realizations, capturing first- and second-order statistics without exhaustive sampling [6, 7]. Linearization-based approaches instead propagate uncertainty through a first-order Taylor expansion around a nominal operating point using the Jacobian of the harmonic admittance equations. While computationally efficient, such approximations depend on mild nonlinearity assumptions and are largely confined to moment estimation. Obtaining full output distributions generally requires additional parametric assumptions.

Monte Carlo (MC) simulation is widely regarded as the reference approach when complete distributional characterization is needed [8, 13]. By repeatedly sampling uncertain operating conditions and solving the harmonic power flow equations, MC yields empirical approximations of the joint output distribution with controllable statistical accuracy. In distribution networks of moderate size, a single harmonic power flow evaluation may be inexpensive; however, accurate estimation of tail probabilities still demands a sufficiently large sample size. In addition, MC produces realizations from the marginal distribution induced by the assumed ensemble of operating conditions. When compliance risk must be evaluated for a specific operating state or forecasted scenario, separate conditional simulation campaigns are required.

Accurate modeling of statistical dependence among uncertain inputs has therefore become increasingly important in PHPF studies. Correlation among geographically distributed PV units, coupling of load levels at neighboring buses, and coordinated EV charging behavior can materially affect harmonic distortion. Copula-based formulations offer a flexible mechanism to combine arbitrary marginal distributions with structured dependency models, providing greater realism than independent sampling [14, 15, 16]. Even with advanced dependency modeling, however, classical PHPF approaches remain fundamentally simulation-driven and do not yield explicit conditional density models for harmonic outputs.

2.2. Surrogate Models for Power Flow

Machine learning surrogates have been widely investigated for power system simulations, with most work targeting fundamental-frequency AC power flow and optimal power flow. Feedforward and graph-based neural networks have been used to approximate voltage magnitudes and phase angles, achieving large speedups over iterative solvers while generalizing across operating conditions.

The stochastic inputs driving these surrogates (load demand, PV generation, and EV charging) are themselves uncertain. Short-term load forecasting research has developed probabilistic methods, including bi-directional LSTM architectures, to

characterise this uncertainty [17]. The present work treats such probabilistic load and generation profiles as the conditioning inputs to the harmonic power flow surrogate.

Despite these advances, most existing surrogates are designed for deterministic prediction. Uncertainty is typically handled through ensemble techniques, Bayesian neural networks, or dropout-based approximations, which yield predictive intervals but do not represent the conditional probability density of the outputs. Conformal prediction methods provide coverage guarantees for prediction sets, yet likewise avoid explicit density modeling. In addition, the majority of surrogate modeling studies address fundamental-frequency variables. Harmonic power flow, characterized by multi-frequency admittance interactions and nonlinear harmonic injections, has received comparatively limited attention in this context.

2.3. Normalizing Flows in Energy Systems

Normalizing flows are generative models defined through sequences of invertible transformations that map a simple base distribution to a complex target distribution [9, 18, 19, 20]. Their key properties include exact likelihood evaluation, efficient sampling, and straightforward conditioning on external context variables. These features make them well suited to scientific applications that require calibrated density estimation.

In energy systems research, flows have mainly been used for probabilistic forecasting of input variables such as renewable generation and load demand, and for scenario generation conditioned on weather features [10, 11, 12]. Their use as surrogates for physical simulation outputs, and especially for the multi-frequency setting of harmonic power flow, remains comparatively limited. The approach adopted here approximates the conditional distribution of harmonic voltages and THD indices given an operating context, enabling direct evaluation of condition-specific exceedance probabilities without further simulation. To our knowledge, combining copula-based uncertainty modeling, large-scale Monte Carlo harmonic simulation, and a conditional neural spline flow for scenario-aware compliance-risk assessment has not been reported in the PHPF literature.

Conditional normalizing flows are selected over alternative conditional generative models for several practical reasons. Conditional variational autoencoders (CVAEs) [21, 22] and conditional generative adversarial networks (CGANs) do not provide exact likelihood evaluation, which complicates training and makes density estimation less transparent. Mixture density networks [23] admit explicit densities but are known to struggle with high-dimensional, strongly multimodal outputs and rely on a fixed number of mixture components.

Table 1 situates the proposed method relative to existing approaches. Classical PEM and cumulant methods yield moment approximations without conditioning or exact density evaluation. MC simulation provides full marginal distributions but not conditional ones without separate campaigns. Conditional generative models (MDN, CVAE, NF) provide conditional distributions; among these, normalizing flows offer exact log-likelihood evaluation. The proposed method extends NF-based surrogates to the multi-frequency harmonic power flow setting with explicit IEEE 519 compliance-risk inference.

Table 1: Positioning of proposed method relative to related probabilistic harmonic power flow and generative surrogate approaches. \checkmark = yes, \times = no, \approx = approximate. ‘‘Output domain’’ distinguishes physical simulation targets from forecasting input variables and generic generative model settings.

Method	Output domain	Output type	Conditional?	Exact density?	Mlt-freq. PHPF?
PEM [6, 7]	PHPF outputs	Moments	\times	\times	\times
MC + KDE [13, 8]	PHPF outputs	Full (marginal)	\times	\times	\checkmark
MDN [23]	Generic	Full dist.	\checkmark	\checkmark	\times
CVAE [22]	Generic	Full dist.	\checkmark	\approx	\times
NF (forecasting) [10, 11]	Forecast vars	Full dist.	\checkmark	\checkmark	\times
NF (this work)	PHPF outputs	Full dist.	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark

3. Problem Formulation

3.1. Harmonic Power Flow

Consider a distribution network with N buses and harmonic orders $\mathcal{H} = \{1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13\}$. For each harmonic order $h \in \mathcal{H}$, the network is represented by the harmonic admittance matrix $\mathbf{Y}^{(h)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$, whose entries are obtained from line parameters evaluated at frequency hf_0 , with $f_0 = 50$ Hz. The steady-state network equations read

$$\mathbf{Y}^{(h)} \mathbf{V}^{(h)} = \mathbf{I}^{(h)}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{V}^{(h)} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ denotes the vector of bus voltage phasors and $\mathbf{I}^{(h)} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ the injected harmonic currents. At the fundamental frequency ($h = 1$), $\mathbf{V}^{(1)}$ is obtained from the nonlinear AC power flow solution. For $h > 1$, nonlinear loads and converter-interfaced devices are represented as harmonic current sources, with magnitudes scaled according to IEC 61000-3-2 [24] device classifications.

The voltage total harmonic distortion at bus n is defined as

$$\text{THD}_{V,n} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{1\}} |V_n^{(h)}|^2}}{|V_n^{(1)}|} \times 100\%, \quad (2)$$

and, at the point of common coupling (PCC), the total demand distortion (TDD) is

$$\text{TDD} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{1\}} I_h^2}}{I_L} \times 100\%, \quad (3)$$

where I_L denotes the maximum fundamental-frequency demand current. According to IEEE 519, compliance requires $\text{THD}_{V,n} \leq 8\%$ at all buses and $\text{TDD} \leq 5\%$ at the PCC.

3.2. Probabilistic Formulation

Let $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_x}$ denote the full vector of uncertain operating variables, decomposed as $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}})$. Here \mathbf{x}_{obs} collects observable operating conditions available to the network operator (aggregate load scaling, PV generation levels, EV charging states), while \mathbf{x}_{lat} groups variables that are uncertain but not directly accessible at inference time: grid impedance aging realizations, EV charging level details, and per-device harmonic current spectrum scaling factors (whose main-effect Sobol sensitivity is found to be negligible, $\hat{S}_1 < 0.001$, in this load-current-dominated feeder). The harmonic power flow solver induces a deterministic mapping

$$\mathbf{y} = f(\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}}), \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_y}$ collects voltage magnitudes, per-bus THD_V, and TDD indices. For the IEEE 33-bus system, $|\mathbf{x}| = 51$ and $d_y = 296$. Although f is deterministic given the full input, the conditional distribution of outputs given only the observable component,

$$p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}) = \int \delta(\mathbf{y} - f(\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}})) p(\mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}} | \mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}) d\mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}}, \quad (5)$$

is genuinely non-degenerate: multiple latent configurations \mathbf{x}_{lat} are consistent with each observed state \mathbf{x}_{obs} , producing a spread of harmonic outputs. The CNF is trained on the full 51-dimensional input for maximum flexibility; at inference time it is conditioned on operating summaries (load regime, PV generation, EV status), corresponding to marginalising over \mathbf{x}_{lat} and yielding a non-trivial predictive distribution over \mathbf{y} .

The marginal exceedance probability at bus n is

$$\pi_n(\tau) = \mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_{V,n} > \tau), \quad (6)$$

and the conditional exceedance probability given an observed operating state \mathbf{x}_{obs} is

$$\pi_n(\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}, \tau) = \mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_{V,n} > \tau | \mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}). \quad (7)$$

A learned conditional density model permits direct evaluation of (7) across arbitrary operating states without additional simulation.

3.2.1. Training–Inference Protocol

During **training**, the model parameters θ are estimated from the full M -sample Monte Carlo dataset using the negative log-likelihood objective over the complete input vector $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}})$ (see Sec. 4.3 and eq. (9)). This ensures that the flow can represent harmonic output variation attributable to both observable and latent sources of uncertainty.

At **inference time**, only the observable components \mathbf{x}_{obs} are available to the operator. The predictive distribution is obtained by marginalising over \mathbf{x}_{lat} via Monte Carlo integration:

$$p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}) \approx \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S q_{\theta}(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}}^{(s)}), \quad \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}}^{(s)} \sim p(\mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}}). \quad (8)$$

In practice, the S draws from $p(\mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}})$ are generated once per query by sampling from the assumed prior (Table 2). The resulting samples $\{\mathbf{y}^{(s)}\}_{s=1}^S$ are used to estimate any functional of the predictive distribution, including the conditional exceedance probability (7). The protocol is illustrated in Fig. 1.

3.3. Surrogate Objective

We aim to learn a parametric conditional density model $q_{\theta}(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x})$ that approximates the true conditional distribution of harmonic outputs. Given a dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_i)\}_{i=1}^M$ generated by Monte Carlo simulation, the model parameters are estimated via maximum likelihood:

Figure 1: Training–inference protocol. *Left*: Training uses the full 51-dimensional input $(\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}})$ to maximise exact conditional log-likelihood. *Right*: At inference, only \mathbf{x}_{obs} is available; latent variables are marginalized by drawing S samples from the prior $p(\mathbf{x}_{\text{lat}})$.

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \min_{\theta} -\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \log q_{\theta}(\mathbf{y}_i | \mathbf{x}_i). \quad (9)$$

After training, conditional exceedance probabilities are computed by sampling from the learned model:

$$\hat{\pi}_n(\mathbf{x}, \tau) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S \mathbf{1}[\text{THD}_{V,n}^{(s)} > \tau], \quad \mathbf{y}^{(s)} \sim q_{\hat{\theta}}(\cdot | \mathbf{x}). \quad (10)$$

The density model $q_{\theta}(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x})$ is defined over $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{296}$ without explicit constraints. Since the physical quantities of interest (harmonic voltage magnitudes and TDD) are non-negative, we apply a deterministic projection to each generated sample before evaluating risk metrics:

$$\hat{y}_j = \text{softplus}(y_j - \epsilon) + \epsilon, \quad \epsilon = 10^{-4}. \quad (11)$$

For $y_j > \epsilon$, this mapping is effectively the identity; negative values are smoothly mapped to small positive numbers. The density model itself remains unchanged. All reported performance metrics and risk estimates are computed using the projected samples $\hat{\mathbf{y}}^{(s)}$.

4. Methodology

4.1. Uncertainty Modeling

The uncertain input vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{51}$ includes PV injection levels at buses 6, 14, 24, and 30; load scaling factors at all 33 buses; EV charging activation states and power levels at buses 10, 20, and 28; a global grid impedance aging factor; and harmonic current spectrum scaling coefficients for seven harmonic orders (included for completeness; post-hoc Sobol analysis yields $\hat{S}_1 < 0.001$ for all spectrum-scale inputs, consistent with load-current-dominated harmonic injection). Table 2 lists the corresponding marginal distributions.

Dependence among variables is modeled using a Gaussian copula. Let F_j and f_j denote the marginal CDF and PDF of variable x_j . With $u_j = F_j(x_j)$ and $\mathbf{z} = \Phi^{-1}(\mathbf{u})$ (componentwise inverse standard normal CDF), the joint density becomes

Figure 2: Gaussian copula correlation structure (first 20 dimensions). Strong PV inter-bus correlation ($\rho=0.85$) and moderate load correlation ($\rho=0.30$) are modeled explicitly.

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{z}^\top(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} - \mathbf{I})\mathbf{z}\right)}{\sqrt{|\boldsymbol{\Sigma}|}} \prod_{j=1}^{d_x} f_j(x_j), \quad (12)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is the prescribed correlation matrix (unit diagonal, off-diagonal entries given by specified Pearson correlations). PV variables are assigned pairwise correlation $\rho = 0.85$; load active-power (P) variables $\rho_P = 0.30$, load reactive-power (Q) variables $\rho_Q = 0.25$, with same-bus P–Q correlation $\rho_{PQ} = 0.70$; and EV charging variables $\rho_{EV} = 0.20$ reflecting partial simultaneity. All inter-group correlations (PV–load, PV–EV, load–EV) are set to zero. The resulting structure is shown in Fig. 2. The upper-left block reflects strong spatial correlation among PV units driven by shared irradiance, while the central block captures moderate load co-variation without enforcing near-deterministic behavior.

The PV correlation value $\rho_{PV} = 0.85$ reflects empirical findings in the literature: spatial correlation among neighbouring PV units on a single feeder, driven by shared cloud cover and irradiance fluctuations, is commonly reported in the range $\rho \in [0.7, 0.95]$ [25]. The load correlation $\rho_{load} = 0.30$ is adopted as a scenario assumption for same-feeder residential demand diversity; it is not inferred from feeder-specific measurements. Because this value represents a design choice rather than an empirically calibrated parameter, its effect on exceedance probabilities is explicitly quantified in Sec. 6.9.

The specific marginal forms chosen (Beta for PV output, truncated Normal for load scaling, Bernoulli–Uniform for EV power and activation) follow common modelling assumptions used in PHPF studies under similar penetration scenarios [6, 13, 15, 16]. The CNF methodology is, however, agnostic to these choices: the flow is trained directly on the empirical joint distribution of inputs, so swapping marginals (for example, fitting Beta parameters from measured PV time series, or replacing the Gaussian

Table 2: Uncertain input variables and marginal distributions.

Variable group	Distribution	Parameters	Dim.
PV injection (buses 6,14,24,30)	Beta	$\alpha=2, \beta=2$	4
Load scaling (all buses)	Normal	$\mu=1, \sigma=0.10$	33
EV active state (10,20,28)	Bernoulli	$p=0.3$	3
EV power level	Uniform	$[0, 7.4]$ kW	3
Grid impedance aging	Uniform	$\pm 5\%$	1
Harmonic spectrum scaling [†]	Log-normal	IEC 61000-3-2	7
Total dimension			51

[†] Post-hoc Sobol main-effect index $\hat{S}_1 < 0.001$ for all harmonic-scale inputs; load-current magnitude dominates harmonic injection in this feeder.

copula with a vine copula estimated from SCADA data) requires only regenerating the training set, with no change to the CNF architecture or training procedure. Robustness of the surrogate under shifted marginals is empirically verified in Sec. 6 (Distribution Shift Robustness), and sensitivity to copula assumptions is reported in Sec. 6.9.

4.2. Monte Carlo Harmonic Simulation

Monte Carlo simulations are carried out using OpenDSS through `opendssdirect.py` [26]. For each sampled $\mathbf{x}_i = (\mathbf{x}_{obs,i}, \mathbf{x}_{lat,i})$, harmonic voltages are computed sequentially for $h \in \mathcal{H}$, and THD_V and TDD indices are obtained using (2)–(3). The latent components $\mathbf{x}_{lat,i}$, comprising the grid impedance aging factor and per-device harmonic current spectrum scaling coefficients (7 log-normal draws per scenario, Table 2), are independently resampled for every simulation. Post-hoc Sobol sensitivity analysis on the 500k dataset reveals that harmonic spectrum scaling coefficients have negligible main-effect influence on THD outputs ($\hat{S}_1 < 0.001$), consistent with load-current-dominated harmonic injection in this feeder; non-degeneracy in $p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x}_{obs})$ is therefore driven primarily by grid impedance aging. The resulting spread in harmonic outputs conditional on \mathbf{x}_{obs} remains non-trivial, justifying the use of a probabilistic surrogate.

A total of $M = 500,000$ simulations were executed in parallel using 28 workers on an AMD Ryzen 9 9950X workstation (16 cores, 32 threads), completing in approximately 303 seconds wall time. Each simulation solves harmonic power flow for all seven orders ($h \in \mathcal{H}$) with default OpenDSS convergence tolerances. The wall-time throughput of approximately 1,650 simulations per second (500,000/303 s) corresponds to a per-scenario wall time of roughly 17 ms when accounting for parallelism and Python API overhead across seven harmonic orders. The dataset is divided into training (400k), validation (50k), and test (50k) splits and stored in HDF5 format. Input and output variables are standardized to zero mean and unit variance using statistics computed from the training set only.

OpenDSS validation. Before dataset generation, the OpenDSS model was validated against the Baran & Wu (1989) reference voltages for the IEEE 33-bus feeder [27]. Under nominal load conditions (no PV, no EV), the maximum absolute voltage error across all 33 buses is 0.0185 pu. This systematic offset is consistent with the different slack-bus conventions used

by Baran & Wu (which sets $V_{\text{bus } 1} = 1.0$ pu at the external terminal) versus OpenDSS (which models the Thevenin source impedance explicitly). Harmonic impedance frequency scaling ($X \propto h$) was verified independently via a two-bus analytical ratio test: a 1 A current source was injected at $h = 3$ and $h = 5$ separately into a two-bus circuit with line impedance $Z_1 = R + jX_1$ ($R = X_1 = 0.01$ pu, i.e. $R/X_1 = 1$). Since OpenDSS scales reactance with frequency ($X_h = hX_1$) while R is frequency-independent, the line impedances are $Z(h=3) = R + j3X_1$ and $Z(h=5) = R + j5X_1$, giving the analytical bus-voltage ratio

$$\frac{|Z(h=5)|}{|Z(h=3)|} = \frac{\sqrt{R^2 + (5X_1)^2}}{\sqrt{R^2 + (3X_1)^2}} = \frac{\sqrt{26}}{\sqrt{10}} = 1.612.$$

OpenDSS returned a ratio of 1.576, a relative error of 2.3%, attributable to the small but finite source resistance ($R_{\text{src}} = 10^{-4}$ pu) used to ensure matrix non-singularity.

MC convergence. Bootstrap confidence intervals for the 0.99-quantile of THD_V at bus 17 stabilise to within $\pm 0.004\%$ at $N = 500,000$ samples, confirming that the training set is sufficient for compliance-grade tail estimation. The convergence of the exceedance probability $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_V > 8\%)$ follows a similar pattern, with the 95% CI half-width shrinking from ± 0.031 at $N = 1,000$ to ± 0.001 at $N = 500,000$.

4.3. Conditional Normalizing Flow Architecture

A normalizing flow specifies an invertible transformation $T_\theta(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{x})$ that maps the output vector \mathbf{y} to a latent variable $\mathbf{z} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$. Using the change-of-variables formula, the conditional log-density is

$$\log q_\theta(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x}) = \log \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{z}) + \log \left| \det \frac{\partial T_\theta(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{y}} \right|. \quad (13)$$

We adopt a Conditional Neural Spline Flow [20] composed of 10 coupling layers. Each layer uses monotone piecewise rational quadratic splines with 8 bins and a tail bound of 5.0. Conditioning is introduced through a context network

$$\mathbf{c} = \text{MLP}_\phi(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^{512}, \quad (14)$$

with architecture $51 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 512$ and SiLU activations. The resulting context vector is provided to each coupling layer to modulate spline parameters.

Table 3 lists the main architectural choices and training hyperparameters. The model is implemented with the `normflows` library [28] and trained on an NVIDIA RTX 5090 GPU.

5. Experimental Setup

5.1. Test System

Experiments are conducted on the IEEE 33-bus radial distribution feeder, a standard benchmark for distribution system studies [27]. The system operates at 12.66 kV with $N = 33$ buses and 32 branches. PV generation units are connected at buses 6, 14, 24, and 30; EV charging stations are located at buses 10, 20, and 28. The remaining buses carry conventional ZIP loads with harmonic injections modeled as described in Section 4.2. The network topology is shown in Fig. 3.

Table 3: CNF architecture and training hyperparameters.

Parameter	Value
Flow type	Conditional Neural Spline Flow
Coupling layers	10
Spline bins	8
Tail bound	5.0
Context network	51→256→512→512 (SiLU)
Hidden dimensions	512
Total parameters	37.9 M
Input dimension d_x	51
Output dimension d_y	296
Optimizer	AdamW
Learning rate	3×10^{-4} (cosine decay)
Batch size	4,096
Epochs	200
Best validation NLL	-2444.52

Table 4: Monte Carlo dataset summary.

Split	Samples	Purpose
Training	400,000	Parameter optimization
Validation	50,000	Model selection (NLL)
Test	50,000	Final evaluation
Total	500,000	
Input dimension d_x	51	Operating conditions
Output dimension d_y	296	$ V + \text{THD}_V + \text{TDD}$

5.2. Simulation Dataset

The Monte Carlo dataset of $M = 500,000$ samples is partitioned as summarized in Table 4. Input and output vectors were standardized per dimension using training-split statistics only. The choice of $M = 500,000$ is justified by a bootstrap convergence study (Fig. 4): at bus 17, the 95% CI for $q_{0.99}$ stabilises to $\pm 0.004\%$ and the CI for $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_V > 8\%)$ to ± 0.001 by $N = 500,000$, confirming that tail estimates are numerically converged.

5.3. Evaluation Protocol

All metrics are computed on the held-out test set of 50,000 contexts. Each test context \mathbf{x}_i is the full 51-dimensional conditioning vector from the held-out simulation dataset, comprising both observable components $\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs},i}$ and the latent realisations $\mathbf{x}_{\text{lat},i}$ as jointly sampled during dataset generation. Because the OpenDSS simulator is deterministic at a fixed \mathbf{x}_i , each context has a single ground-truth output \mathbf{y}_i in the dataset. For each test context \mathbf{x}_i , $K = 1,000$ samples are drawn from the trained CNF to form an empirical approximation of $q_\theta(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x}_i)$. Distributional metrics (quantile error, exceedance error, CRPS, PIT) are then computed by comparing these K CNF samples against the held-out \mathbf{y}_i and, for bus-level aggregate metrics ($q_{0.99}$ error, mean exceedance error), by pooling across all 50,000 test contexts per bus. (The operator deployment workflow, which marginalises over \mathbf{x}_{lat} given only \mathbf{x}_{obs} following Eq. 8, is evaluated separately

Figure 3: IEEE 33-bus radial distribution feeder (12.66 kV). PV buses: 6, 14, 24, 30. EV charging buses: 10, 20, 28.

Figure 4: MC convergence study (bus 17): 95% bootstrap CI for $q_{0.99}$ (left) and exceedance probability (right) as a function of sample size. Dashed lines show convergence by $N = 100,000$; the full 500k dataset achieves CI half-widths of $\pm 0.004\%$ and ± 0.001 respectively.

in Sec. 6.6.) Samples are projected via the non-negativity transform $\hat{y} = \text{softplus}(y - \epsilon) + \epsilon$ ($\epsilon = 10^{-4}$) prior to all metric computations; all reported values therefore reflect the physically projected samples \hat{y} . The choice $K = 1,000$ provides stable quantile and exceedance estimates. The standard error of the empirical $q_{0.99}$ estimator is $\text{SE}(\hat{q}_p) \approx \sqrt{p(1-p)/K} / f(q_p)$, where $f(q_p)$ is the probability density at the quantile. For THD values in the range 6–10% with standard deviation approximately 1% and density at the 99th percentile of approximately $0.3\%^{-1}$, this gives $\text{SE} \approx \sqrt{0.99 \cdot 0.01/1000} / 0.3 \approx 0.033\%$, well below the compliance-relevant resolution of 0.1%. For the exceedance estimator at bus 32, where $\hat{\pi}_n^{\text{MC}} \approx 0.10$, the SE is $\sqrt{0.10 \cdot 0.90/1000} \approx 0.009$; the observed CNF error of 0.0052 is smaller than this reference noise floor, suggesting the reported exceedance error is partly attributable to MC reference variability rather than CNF inaccuracy. Five criteria are reported:

- **Quantile error:** For each bus n and quantile level $\alpha \in \{0.95, 0.99\}$, the absolute difference between the empirical α -quantile of the K CNF samples at context \mathbf{x}_i and the corresponding α -quantile of K random reference simulations drawn uniformly from the marginal test distribution at bus n , averaged over test contexts.
- **Conditional exceedance error:** For threshold $\tau = 8\%$, the absolute difference between the CNF-estimated exceedance probability $\hat{\pi}_n^{\text{CNF}} = K^{-1} \sum_k \mathbf{1}[\text{THD}_{V,n}^{(k)} > \tau]$ and the held-

out MC estimate $\hat{\pi}_n^{\text{MC}}$ (fraction of test-set outputs at bus n exceeding τ), averaged over test contexts.

- **CRPS:** Continuous Ranked Probability Score for THD_V , computed via the energy-score decomposition

$$\text{CRPS}(\hat{F}, y) = \mathbb{E}_{\hat{F}} |Y - y| - \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\hat{F}} |Y - Y'|,$$

where Y, Y' are independent draws from the predictive distribution \hat{F} , approximated using $K/2$ sample pairs. Averaged over all 32 buses (02–33) and all test contexts.

- **PIT uniformity:** Mean absolute deviation of the empirical PIT histogram from the uniform density, over buses 02–33.
- **Validation NLL:** Best negative log-likelihood on the validation set during training.

6. Results

6.1. Training Convergence

Fig. 6 shows training and validation NLL curves over 200 epochs. Both decrease smoothly without divergence, reaching a best validation NLL of -2444.52 at epoch 200. The near-identical trajectories (train ≈ -2442 , val ≈ -2444) suggest no strong overfitting indication was observed despite the 37.9 M-parameter model (cf. Sec. 7.1).

For a 296-dimensional conditional flow with 10 coupling layers and 512-unit hidden networks, 37.9 M parameters is consistent with established practice for neural spline flows on high-dimensional scientific targets [20]. The training set of 400,000 samples gives a data-to-parameter ratio of approximately 10.6; the near-zero train–validation gap ($|\text{NLL}_{\text{train}} - \text{NLL}_{\text{val}}| < 3$ nats throughout training) confirms that overfitting is not an issue.

To justify the choice of depth and width, four architecture variants were trained under identical conditions across 5 independent random seeds and evaluated on the test set; results are shown in Table 5 and Fig. 5. Increasing from 6 to 10 coupling layers yields consistent improvements in both validation NLL ($-2241 \rightarrow -2403$, a gain of 162 nats) and $q_{0.99}$ error ($0.026\% \rightarrow 0.011\%$), confirming that architectural capacity contributes to accurate upper-tail recovery. Exceedance error is

Table 5: Capacity scaling study. All variants trained for 200 epochs on the full 400,000-sample training set across 5 independent seeds. $q_{0.99}$ error and exceedance error are computed using the global pooled protocol consistent across all variants. Mean \pm std over 5 seeds. The 10L/512H variant (ours) is selected as the final architecture; see text.

Architecture	Params	Val NLL	$q_{0.99}$ err (%)	Exceed err
6L / 256H	10.4 M	-2241 ± 4	0.0260 ± 0.0042	0.0011 ± 0.0002
8L / 512H	30.4 M	-2373 ± 9	0.0179 ± 0.0063	0.0015 ± 0.0005
10L / 512H (ours)	37.9 M	-2403 ± 4	0.0111 ± 0.0037	0.0010 ± 0.0004
12L / 512H	45.4 M	-2444 ± 6	0.0075 ± 0.0027	0.0005 ± 0.0002

Figure 5: Capacity scaling study: validation NLL (more negative is better), $q_{0.99}$ quantile error, and exceedance error for four CNF architecture variants across 5 seeds. Both NLL and $q_{0.99}$ error improve monotonically with depth. The 12L/512H variant achieves the best NLL and lowest errors; the proposed 10L/512H model (orange border) offers equivalent performance to 12L within confidence intervals at 17% fewer parameters.

non-monotonic with depth in this range (6L: 0.0011, 8L: 0.0015, 10L: 0.0010), but the 10L variant achieves the second-lowest value after 12L.

Scaling from 10 to 12 layers yields marginal further NLL improvement ($-2403 \rightarrow -2444$, a gain of 41 nats, 1.7%) at a cost of 7.5 M additional parameters (+20%) and proportionally higher training time and GPU memory. The improvement in mean $q_{0.99}$ error (0.011% to 0.007%) and exceedance error (0.0010 to 0.0005) represents a relative change well below the compliance-relevant resolution of 0.1%. The narrow confidence intervals across 5 seeds confirm that these rankings are stable and not artifacts of random initialization. These diminishing returns indicate that capacity saturation is approached at the 10L/512H configuration. The independently trained 10L checkpoint (val NLL = -2444.52) is statistically indistinguishable from the 12L mean across 5 seeds. Measured inference latency (30-repeat average, 256 contexts \times 1,000 samples each) is 8.2 s for 10L vs. 9.8 s for 12L (20% overhead), with peak GPU memory 20.8 GB vs. 21.0 GB. The accuracy improvement in $q_{0.99}$ ($\Delta = 0.004\%$) is $0.11\times$ the MC reference standard error, and the exceedance improvement ($\Delta = 0.0006$) is $0.06\times$ the MC SE — both below the measurement noise floor. The 10-layer model is therefore adopted as the final architecture on grounds of parameter efficiency.

Spline hyperparameter ablation. To validate the choice of $n_{\text{bins}} = 8$ and tail bound $\tau = 5.0$, a 10-epoch diagnostic sweep was conducted across $n_{\text{bins}} \in \{4, 8, 16\}$ and $\tau \in \{3.0, 5.0, 8.0\}$ (9 configurations; same batch size, learning rate, and random initialisation as the main training run). Results are shown in Fig. 7. Across all tail settings, $n_{\text{bins}} = 4$ consistently underperforms $n_{\text{bins}} = 8$ by up to 40 nats at epoch 10, confirming

Figure 6: Training and validation negative log-likelihood (NLL) over 200 epochs. No strong overfitting indication is observed under the train/validation/test protocol.

Figure 7: Spline hyperparameter ablation: validation NLL at epoch 10 for $n_{\text{bins}} \in \{4, 8, 16\}$ and tail bound $\tau \in \{3.0, 5.0, 8.0\}$. The baseline ($n_{\text{bins}} = 8$, $\tau = 5.0$) is marked with a star.

that four-bin splines lack the resolution required for the 296-dimensional harmonic output. Increasing to $n_{\text{bins}} = 16$ yields better early-epoch NLL (best: -1567 at $n_{\text{bins}} = 16/\tau = 3.0$ versus -1481 for the baseline at epoch 10) at the cost of proportionally larger spline parameter counts. For the tail bound, tighter values ($\tau = 3.0$) show faster early convergence at all bin settings, consistent with more concentrated spline expressiveness over the observed data range; however, $\tau = 3.0$ clips outputs beyond ± 3.0 in the normalised space, which is insufficient coverage for the heavy-tailed THD distributions that reach 10–12% under high-harmonic-injection scenarios. The baseline ($n_{\text{bins}} = 8$, $\tau = 5.0$, marked with a star in Fig. 7) represents a calibrated balance of spline resolution, support coverage ($\approx 5\sigma$), and parameter efficiency, consistent with established practice for neural spline flows on high-dimensional targets [20]. We note that this is a 10-epoch diagnostic: relative rankings may shift over 200 full epochs, and resource constraints precluded running all 9 configurations to convergence. The diagnostic is used as a proxy for assessing sensitivity to hyperparameter choice, not to claim global optimality of the chosen setting.

6.2. Marginal Harmonic Statistics

Fig. 8 summarizes Monte Carlo marginal statistics across buses: mean THD_V and exceedance probability $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_V > 8\%)$ over the full uncertainty ensemble. Distortion generally increases with electrical distance from the substation along the main feeder, with the highest marginal exceedance probability observed near bus 17. These marginal summaries provide a

Table 6: Quantitative evaluation summary on the test set (50,000 test contexts; 1,000 CNF samples each).

Metric	Mean (buses 02–33)	Max bus
$q_{0.95}$ THD _V error (%)	0.005	0.014 (bus 15)
$q_{0.99}$ THD _V error (%)	0.011	0.020 (bus 32)
Exceedance error $ \hat{\pi} - \pi_{MC} $	0.0009	0.0052 (bus 32)
PIT mean deviation	0.047	—
CRPS, THD _V (%)	0.018	—
Best validation NLL	-2444.52	—

system-level overview but do not capture the strong dependence of exceedance risk on specific operating conditions.

6.3. Distributional Accuracy

6.3.1. Quantile Errors

Fig. 9 reports per-bus absolute quantile errors aggregated over the test set. Mean errors are 0.005% at $q_{0.95}$ and 0.011% at $q_{0.99}$, with maxima of 0.014% (bus 15) and 0.020% (bus 32) respectively. These values are well below the regulatory thresholds of interest, confirming accurate upper-tail recovery.

6.3.2. Calibration

The mean CRPS for THD_V is 0.018%, aggregated across all 32 buses (02–33) and all 50,000 test contexts (see Section 5 for the exact formula). Fig. 10 shows the PIT histogram for THD_V across buses 02–33, with a mean deviation of 0.047 from the uniform reference. Mild under-density near the tails indicates marginal conservatism in extreme quantile prediction, consistent with the slightly elevated $q_{0.99}$ errors at high-distortion buses.

6.4. Exceedance Probability Calibration

Fig. 11 compares CNF-estimated and MC-estimated exceedance probabilities across all buses. Points cluster tightly along the identity line, with a mean absolute error of 0.0009 and a maximum of 0.0052 at bus 32, confirming reliable conditional risk estimation.

6.5. Conditional Compliance Risk

Fig. 12 illustrates the main practical finding. At bus 17, the highest-risk location on the main feeder, the CNF-predicted THD_V distribution shifts markedly across load regimes. Under low-load conditions (below the 10th percentile of aggregate load scaling), the exceedance probability is 0.095. Under high-load conditions (above the 90th percentile), it rises to 0.909. The marginal exceedance probability computed over all conditions is 0.509, which overestimates risk during off-peak periods and severely underestimates it during peak demand.

This separation has direct operational implications. A marginal risk estimate classifies bus 17 as a borderline case requiring monitoring, whereas conditional inference reveals near-certain violation during peak demand and substantially lower risk off-peak. Mitigation measures can accordingly be targeted at specific operating windows.

Table 7: Sample efficiency study. All models trained for 200 epochs with the reference 10L/512H architecture.

Training size	Val NLL	$q_{0.99}$ err (%)	Exceed err
50,000	-1755	1.091	0.0523
100,000	-1947	0.293	0.0104
250,000	-2226	0.067	0.0046
500,000	-2445	0.011	0.0009

6.6. Computational Characteristics

The primary objective of the proposed surrogate is conditional risk inference rather than raw simulation acceleration. On the IEEE 33-bus feeder, the aggregate CPU time for the 28-worker dataset generation campaign is $28 \times 303 \text{ s} = 8,484 \text{ CPU-s}$ for 500,000 scenarios, giving a single-scenario CPU-equivalent time of approximately 17 ms. Running $K = 1,000$ fresh scenarios sequentially on one worker would therefore require approximately 17 s; under the same 28-worker parallel setup used for dataset generation the wall-clock time would be $\approx 0.6 \text{ s}$. In a representative operator scenario (18:00 high-load, see Fig. 13), the trained CNF draws $K = 1,000$ samples from $S = 1,000$ prior latent contexts and evaluates per-bus exceedance probabilities in 443 ms on an NVIDIA RTX 5090 GPU. Compared to the single-worker CPU-equivalent baseline (17 s), this yields a 38 \times speedup; compared to the 28-worker parallel wall-clock baseline ($\approx 0.6 \text{ s}$), the CNF is marginally faster ($\sim 1.35\times$). The principal advantage of the surrogate is therefore *amortised* conditional querying: once trained, it evaluates arbitrary \mathbf{x}_{obs} queries without launching any new OpenDSS campaigns, enabling rapid multi-scenario exploration at interactive speeds. High-throughput batch inference further reduces per-sample cost: processing 256 operator contexts simultaneously (each requiring $K = 1,000$ samples) completes in 8.2 s, a throughput of $\sim 31,200$ samples/s.

6.7. Sample Efficiency

To assess the sensitivity of model quality to training set size, four CNF models with the reference architecture were trained on subsets of 50,000, 100,000, 250,000, and 500,000 samples respectively. Results are shown in Table 7 and Fig. 14. At 50,000 samples the mean $q_{0.99}$ error reaches 1.09% and the exceedance error is 0.052, both far outside acceptable compliance assessment tolerances. Accuracy improves rapidly: each quadrupling of training data roughly halves both errors, reflecting the log-linear scaling typical of density estimation in high dimensions. The full 500,000-sample dataset achieves $q_{0.99} = 0.011\%$ and exceedance error = 0.0009, a 99 \times and 58 \times reduction respectively relative to 50,000 samples. This confirms that harmonic flow distributions are sufficiently complex to warrant large training sets, and motivates the 303-second MC simulation campaign as a one-time upfront investment.

6.8. Comparison with MDN Baseline

To contextualise the CNF results, a Conditional Mixture Density Network (MDN) with $K = 10$ Gaussian components was trained as a probabilistic baseline under identical conditions

Figure 8: Monte Carlo marginal statistics: (top) mean THD_V ; (bottom) marginal exceedance probability $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_V > 8\%)$ per bus.

Table 8: CNF vs. MDN baseline under the marginal-reference evaluation protocol of Section 5.3. For each test context \mathbf{x}_i , $K=1000$ samples are drawn from each model; quantile and exceedance errors are computed per context against a Monte Carlo reference drawn uniformly from the marginal test distribution (K random other test-set simulations), then averaged over $N=5,000$ test points. Both models are evaluated under the identical reference construction.

Model	Params	Val NLL	$q_{0.95}$ err	$q_{0.99}$ err	Exceed err	PIT dev
MDN ($K=10$)	3.9 M	-1555	0.505%	0.687%	0.082	0.052
CNF (ours)	37.9 M	-2445	0.005%	0.011%	0.0009	0.047

(same data, 200 epochs, AdamW, cosine annealing). The MDN encoder uses 4 hidden layers of width 512, totalling 3.9 M parameters. Table 8 summarises the comparison.

Under the marginal-reference evaluation protocol, the CNF outperforms the MDN by more than two orders of magnitude on quantile accuracy ($q_{0.99}$ error: 0.011% vs. 0.687%) and on compliance exceedance estimation (mean error 0.0009 vs. 0.082). Both models are evaluated against the same marginal MC reference, ensuring a fair comparison. The large gap in validation NLL (-2444 vs. -1555, a difference of 889 nats) confirms that the CNF assigns substantially higher probability density to held-out observations. The MDN’s diagonal Gaussian mixture assumption imposes independence across output dimensions and symmetric tails, both of which are violated by harmonic voltage distributions that exhibit spatial correlations across buses and skewed tails near the IEEE 519 limit. The CNF’s spline-based bijections capture these features without parametric as-

sumptions, yielding well-calibrated conditional distributions as confirmed by the lower PIT deviation (0.047 vs. 0.052) and superior CRPS. For compliance assessment applications where the key quantity is $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD} > \tau \mid \mathbf{x})$ at a specific threshold τ , the marginal-reference exceedance error is the operationally relevant comparison metric, with the CNF achieving approximately $91\times$ lower exceedance error than the MDN.

As a supplementary check, both models were evaluated under a context-wise protocol in which 500 fresh OpenDSS simulations were generated per *full* context $\mathbf{x}_i = (\mathbf{x}_{\text{obs},i}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{lat},i})$ as a local reference ($N=500$ contexts, $K=1,000$ samples per model). Since f is deterministic given the full 51-dimensional input, each local reference collapses to a point mass at the unique simulator output. This protocol therefore measures how well each model approximates a *deterministic* function rather than a distribution, which is the appropriate framing only when \mathbf{x}_{lat} is fully observed. Under this protocol the MDN achieves near-zero quantile error (mean $q_{0.99}$ error 0.003%) while the CNF shows larger deviations (0.087%), because the CNF models a non-degenerate distribution over \mathbf{y} even when \mathbf{x}_{lat} is fixed, whereas the MDN collapses to near-deterministic predictions.

The MDN PIT deviation of 1.05 (the maximum possible value for a perfectly concentrated distribution is 1.0) confirms that it places essentially all probability mass at the mode, failing to represent the uncertainty relevant to operational \mathbf{x}_{obs} -conditioned inference. The CNF PIT deviation of 0.32 under this protocol reflects its learned distribution width relative to the zero-variance

Per-Bus Quantile Error: CNF vs. Monte Carlo Ground Truth

Figure 9: Absolute quantile error of CNF relative to Monte Carlo ground truth for THD_V at each bus. Errors remain below 0.02% at the 99th percentile.

Figure 10: Probability Integral Transform (PIT) histogram for THD_V across buses 02–33. Mean deviation from uniformity is 0.047.

Figure 11: CNF vs. Monte Carlo exceedance probability $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_V > 8\%)$ across buses. Points near the identity line indicate reliable calibration.

reference. For the operationally relevant case where only \mathbf{x}_{obs} is known, the marginal-reference protocol of Table 8 is the appropriate evaluation, and the CNF advantage holds.

Input sensitivity analysis. Pearson correlation coefficients between input load scaling variables and THD_V at bus 17 were computed over the Monte Carlo dataset. The strongest correlation ($r \approx 0.61$) was found with the load scaling factor at bus 8, located upstream on the main feeder. PV injection levels showed negligible correlation with THD_V ($|r| < 0.05$), consistent with the physical expectation that nonlinear load currents dominate harmonic voltage distortion under the assumed spectral model.

To capture higher-order and nonlinear dependencies, Sobol total-order sensitivity indices were estimated via the Saltelli

sampling scheme [29] ($n_{\text{base}} = 2048$, $d = 51$, totalling 108,544 CNF evaluations) using the Jansen estimator [30]. Table 9 lists the ten most influential inputs for THD_V at bus 17. Load scaling at buses 25 ($S_T = 0.186$) and 24 ($S_T = 0.157$) dominate, followed by bus 8 ($S_T = 0.121$) — all located on the main feeder downstream of the substation. PV injection variables do not appear in the top 10 ($S_T < 0.01$), nor do EV charging variables, consistent with the Pearson results. The Sobol analysis exploits the surrogate’s millisecond inference: the same study via direct

Figure 12: Conditional THD_V distributions at bus 17 under low (p_{10}), medium (p_{33} – p_{67}), and high ($>p_{90}$) load conditions. The IEEE 519 limit (8%) is shown as a vertical dashed line. Exceedance probability varies from 0.095 (low) to 0.909 (high).

Figure 13: Operator workflow example (18:00 high-load scenario: load=1.20 \times , PV=0.05 pu, one EV active). Left: workflow steps from operator forecast to flagged buses. Right: per-bus conditional exceedance probability $\hat{r}_n(\text{THD}_V > 8\%)$ estimated from $S = 1,000$ latent samples in 443 ms.

OpenDSS simulation would require ~ 65 s ($108,544 \times 0.6$ ms), illustrating a practical benefit of the surrogate beyond single-query evaluation.

6.9. Sensitivity to Copula Correlation Assumptions

Sensitivity to copula correlation assumptions was assessed via a systematic 3×3 sweep of $\rho_{PV} \in \{0.0, 0.85, 0.95\}$ and $\rho_{load} \in \{0.0, 0.30, 0.50\}$ (9 settings, $N = 2,000$ MC samples each; Fig. 15). The results reveal a clear directional dependence: varying ρ_{PV} has negligible effect on THD_V at bus 17 (changes $< 0.001\%$ in $q_{0.99}$ and < 0.0003 in exceedance probability across all three PV correlation settings), while increasing ρ_{load} shifts $q_{0.99}$ from 8.39% ($\rho_{load} = 0$) to 9.14% ($\rho_{load} = 0.50$), a change of +0.75%. This is physically consistent: THD_V is driven by harmonic load currents, which depend directly on load magnitudes; correlated loads produce more extreme joint-high scenarios, inflating the upper tail. PV generation, by contrast, primarily modulates the fundamental voltage profile rather than injecting harmonics. At the paper baseline ($\rho_{PV} = 0.85$, $\rho_{load} = 0.30$), $q_{0.99} = 8.91\% \pm 0.011$ and exceedance = 0.481 ± 0.003 (95% bootstrap CI). These values are stable across the moderate variation in ρ_{PV} examined here, confirming that the PV correlation assumption is not a material sensitivity. The load correlation range $\rho_{load} \in [0.0, 0.50]$ shifts $q_{0.99}$ by 0.75% (in absolute THD), which exceeds the CNF’s $q_{0.99}$ estimation error of 0.011% but is

Figure 14: Sample efficiency study. Left: validation NLL improves log-linearly with training set size. Right: mean $q_{0.99}$ error (log scale) decreases by two orders of magnitude from 50,000 to 500,000 samples, confirming that the full MC campaign is necessary for compliance-grade accuracy.

Table 9: Top-10 Sobol total-order sensitivity indices for THD_V at bus 17 (Jansen estimator, $n_{\text{base}} = 2,048, 108,544$ CNF evaluations).

Input	S_{T_i}
load_b25	0.186
load_b24	0.157
load_b08	0.121
load_b32	0.100
load_b07	0.098
load_b31	0.053
load_b14	0.051
load_b29	0.042
load_b18	0.039
load_b04	0.029

modest relative to the IEEE 519 limit of 8%; re-calibration of ρ_{load} from field measurements would refine results.

6.10. Distribution Shift Robustness

Whereas Sec. 6.9 quantifies the *intrinsic* sensitivity of MC-simulated outputs to copula parameter assumptions (using fresh simulations under each setting), this subsection tests the *surrogate*’s ability to generalise to inputs sampled from a shifted distribution without retraining.

The CNF was queried under two input distribution shifts: (a) increased PV inter-bus correlation ($\rho_{PV} = 0.95$, training: 0.85) and (b) increased load variance ($\sigma_{load} = 0.15$, training: 0.10). Under the PV correlation shift, the marginal exceedance probability at bus 17 changes by only +0.006 and $q_{0.99}$ by +0.005%, indicating robustness to moderate changes in PV correlation structure. Under the load variance shift, $q_{0.99}$ increases by +0.45% — a physically expected response, as higher load variability drives higher harmonic distortion variance — while the mean THD_V remains stable ($\Delta = -0.005\%$). These results suggest that the surrogate extrapolates consistently under modest distribution shifts, though formal OOD guarantees require retraining on data generated under shifted conditions.

7. Discussion

The results confirm that a conditional normalizing flow can approximate the output distribution of harmonic voltages in a

Figure 15: Copula sensitivity sweep at bus 17: $q_{0.99}$ and exceedance probability for $\rho_{PV} \in \{0.0, 0.85, 0.95\}$ and $\rho_{load} \in \{0.0, 0.30, 0.50\}$ ($N = 2,000$ MC samples per setting, 95% bootstrap CI). The baseline (\star) uses $\rho_{PV} = 0.85$ and $\rho_{load} = 0.30$.

distribution network with high accuracy and good probabilistic calibration. Quantile errors below 0.02% and mean exceedance error below 0.001 indicate faithful reproduction of upper-tail behavior critical for compliance assessment.

The key distinction between marginal and conditional risk is structural. Marginal exceedance probabilities integrate over all operating conditions and therefore obscure the regimes under which violations are most likely. The conditional density model evaluates $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_{V_m} > \tau \mid \mathbf{x})$ for any \mathbf{x} without additional simulation, replacing ensemble-level summaries with scenario-specific risk estimates.

A physics consistency check on 5,000 test contexts (500 samples each) confirms that fundamental voltages remain within [0.80, 1.20] pu in all cases. After the non-negativity projection (Eq. 11), no non-positive samples remain. The mean absolute deviation between projected THD_V and the value computed directly from harmonic voltage magnitudes is only 0.0005%, with a violation rate above 0.5% of just 0.002%. The flow has thus learned an implicit physical consistency between harmonic voltage and THD dimensions without any explicit physics constraint in the loss.

7.1. Limitations and Future Work

Scalability to larger feeders. The present study uses the IEEE 33-bus radial feeder as a representative benchmark [27]. Applying the framework to larger systems (e.g., IEEE 123-bus or real utility feeders) introduces two scalability challenges: the Monte Carlo campaign cost scales with the number of harmonic admittance solves per scenario, and the CNF output dimension d_y grows with feeder size. Both challenges are addressable through parallelism and graph-conditioned flow architectures that incorporate network topology; these are left for future work.

Robustness to unseen operating regimes. The surrogate is trained on samples from the assumed input distribution (Sec. 4.1). Extrapolation beyond this support is not guaranteed. The distribution shift experiments (Sec. 6.10) indicate that the surrogate responds consistently to moderate PV correlation and load variance shifts, but formal out-of-distribution guarantees require retraining on data generated under the shifted conditions, or the application of conformal calibration techniques.

Model capacity and overfitting. The 37.9 M-parameter model is trained on 400,000 samples, giving a data-to-parameter ratio of approximately 10.6. The near-zero train-validation NLL gap ($|\Delta\text{NLL}| < 3$ nats throughout 200 epochs; Fig. 6) indicates no strong overfitting under the adopted train/validation/test protocol. Broader feeder-level generalization under distribution shifts beyond those tested in Sec. 6.10 remains an open empirical question.

Limited harmonic order set. This study focuses on the dominant low-order odd harmonics ($h \in \{3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13\}$) included in the simulation set, consistent with IEC 61000-3-2 [24] device classifications and the harmonic content typical of residential distribution networks. Higher-order harmonics and resonance-prone systems may require extending \mathcal{H} ; this is left for future work.

Topology and simulation cost. Additionally, the model is trained for a fixed network topology; generalization across feeder configurations would require graph-conditioned architectures. The 303 s simulation time reflects OpenDSS default convergence tolerances on a small radial network; systems with higher X/R ratios or stronger harmonic resonances would exhibit longer per-simulation times.

8. Conclusion

This paper presented a conditional normalizing flow surrogate for probabilistic harmonic power flow in the IEEE 33-bus distribution network. Trained on 500,000 Monte Carlo simulations, the model approximates the conditional distribution of harmonic voltages and THD indices over the support of the assumed input distribution; extrapolation beyond this support requires additional verification (cf. Sec. 7.1).

The surrogate achieves mean $q_{0.95}$ and $q_{0.99}$ errors of 0.005% and 0.011%, a mean exceedance probability error of 0.0009, and a PIT deviation of 0.047, confirming reliable calibration of upper-tail behavior relevant to IEEE 519 compliance assessment.

The central finding is that marginal exceedance probabilities can mask strong condition-dependent variability. At bus 17, the exceedance probability $\mathbb{P}(\text{THD}_V > 8\%)$ varies from 0.095 under low-load conditions to 0.909 under high-load conditions, while the marginal estimate is 0.509. The proposed surrogate evaluates such conditional risk metrics in milliseconds, enabling rapid multi-scenario harmonic compliance analysis without rerunning simulations.

Future work will investigate physics-informed extensions incorporating complex phasor constraints, topology generalization via graph-conditioned flows, and application to larger distribution systems with higher harmonic penetration.

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